

The Gibbs Adsorption Equation and the Concept of the Gibbs Surface Excess

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A critical review of the Gibbs adsorption equation and the concept of the Gibbs surface excess have been presented. Relations between the surface excesses with the absolute composition of the interfacial phase of a binary solution has been discussed for water-organic liquid mixture and water-inorganic salt mixture. The interfacial phase for the water-organic solute mixture is a monolayer whereas that for the water-electrolyte mixture is multilayer in nature. The pressure area curves for charged and uncharged organic monobasic and dibasic acid monolayers at the oil-water and air-water interfaces have been examined in terms of limiting co-area, cohesive pressure, electrical free energy changes, counter-ion binding etc. The forms of the Gibbs adsorption equations for the multicomponent electrolyte solutions in terms of the kT -coefficient have been discussed and its fields of applicability have been pointed out.

ON the occasion of the sixty-fifth birth anniversary of Professor Sushil Kumar Mukherjee, it is indeed a great pleasure for me to present this paper in which our works carried out in the Jadavpur University for last sixteen years have been reviewed. As early as 1950, Professor Mukherjee had drawn my attention to the modern concepts of the stability and the electrical double layer of the colloidal system proposed by Verwey and Overbeek¹. He also pointed out to me during this period the scientific challenge still remaining hidden in the classical and philosophical concept of the Gibbs surface excess². I had always some stimulating discussions with him on these two topics which helped us in achieving some results of both theoretical and experimental interest in this research area.

The Gibbs Surface Excess :

Willard Gibbs³ introduced the concept of the surface excess of a component in a multicomponent solution by imaginarily dividing a column of such liquid with the help of a mathematical plane. Guggenheim and Adam⁴ pointed out certain difficulties associated with the physical concepts of the Gibbs surface excess quantities. Alternative derivations of the Gibbs adsorption equations on various thermodynamic grounds have been proposed by Guggenheim⁵ and others^{6,7}.

In two recent papers, Chattoraj and Moulik^{8,9} have made fresh attempts to clarify the concept of the Gibbs excess for a liquid column containing n_1^t and n_2^t moles of aqueous and non-aqueous components respectively. The Gibbs surface

excess quantities Γ_1 and Γ_2 for this column may then be defined as

$$\Gamma_1 = n_1^t - n_2^t \frac{X_1}{X_2} \quad \dots (1)$$

$$\Gamma_2 = n_2^t - n_1^t \frac{X_2}{X_1} \quad \dots (2)$$

where X_1 and X_2 are the bulk mole fractions of the aqueous and non-aqueous phases respectively. If the interfacial phase of this liquid column is actually composed of $\Delta n_1'$ and $\Delta n_2'$ moles of these two components, then it can be shown from the thermodynamic analysis^{8,9}, that

$$\Gamma_1 = \Delta n_1' - \Delta n_2' \frac{X_1}{X_2} \quad \dots (3)$$

$$\Gamma_2 = \Delta n_2' - \Delta n_1' \frac{X_2}{X_1} \quad \dots (4)$$

The equivalencies between the right sides of equations (1) and (3) as well as those of equations (2) and (4) may directly follow from the clear treatment given by Defay and Prigogine⁶. Both these sets of equations lead to the well-known Guggenheim-Adam relation⁴

$$\Gamma_1 X_2 + \Gamma_2 X_1 = 0 \quad \dots (5)$$

This equation points out that unlike $\Delta n_1'$ and $\Delta n_2'$, Γ_1 and Γ_2 are relative quantities. If at a given composition of the liquid in the column, Γ_2 is positive and definite Γ_1 becomes negative and fixed and vice versa^{8,9}.

Organic components such as ethyl alcohol, methyl alcohol, propyl alcohol, formic acid, acetone, pyridine and glycerol are found to lower the surface tension γ of water during mixing process⁹. Γ_2 for such mixture may be calculated from the Gibbs adsorption equation (6) derived on thermodynamic grounds for the two-component mixture system.

$$\Gamma_2 = - \frac{f_2 X_2}{RT} \frac{d\gamma}{df_2 X_2} \quad \dots (6)$$

Here f_2 stands for the rational activity coefficient of component 2 which for organic components may be obtained from the vapor pressure data. Γ_2 calculated from the experimental data using equation (6) is positive so that negative value of Γ_1 at a given composition of the liquid may be calculated from equation (5). For water mixed in varying amounts with an organic liquid such as pyridine, formic acid, methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol or propyl alcohol, Γ_1 is observed to vary linearly with X_1/X_2 in the wide range of mole ratio composition of the mixture. From the slope and intercept of the linear plot, $\Delta n'_1$ and $\Delta n'_2$ may be calculated with the help of equation (3). Analysis of the results further indicates that the bound liquid components in the interfacial phase form a monomolecular layer⁹ so that the effective cross sectional area of the oriented organic molecule at the interface may be computed. Validity of the monolayer model for the surface phase allows the calculation of $\Delta n'_1$ and $\Delta n'_2$ even when Γ_1 versus X_1/X_2 plot is non-linear.

It is also well-known that the addition of inorganic electrolytes in large amount to water increases the surface tension of the aqueous system significantly. From the slope of the γ -C curves for such electrolyte systems⁸, Γ_2 may be calculated with the help of equation (6). Γ_2 becomes obviously negative indicating preferential adsorption of component 1 in the interfacial phase. Values of the positive excess of water (Γ_1) may be easily calculated using equation (5). In certain ranges of electrolyte concentration Γ_2 is observed to vary linearly with X_2/X_1 so that the absolute interfacial compositions $\Delta n'_1$ and $\Delta n'_2$ may be obtained from the values of the slope and intercept. Such compositions for aqueous systems containing LiCl, NaCl, KCl, NaBr, NaNO₃, K₂SO₄, MgCl₂, MgSO₄ and Al₂(SO₄)₃ have been reported. The interfacial phase is observed to contain multilayers of water. The number of adsorbed layers are observed to increase with increase of the valency of the electrolytes. Further, unlike bulk phase behaviour the adsorbed water seems to have extremely low solubility for adsorbed electrolytes so that $\Delta n'_2$ is negligibly small⁸. Our interpretation of the Gibbs surface excesses for organic solutes and inorganic electrolyte is recently found to be of utmost importance for thermodynamic interpretation of the bending phenomena in the biological systems¹⁰⁻¹⁴.

Soluble monolayer :

The boundary between two homogeneous phases

may be imagined to be a film of a characteristic thickness within which the free surface energy is developed. Water soluble amphipathic organic molecules or ions have the tendency to be preferentially accumulated within this interfacial phase as a result of which adsorbed monolayer of these compounds is formed. The physico-chemical features of the soluble neutral and ionised monolayers have been extensively studied by many workers¹⁵. However, interfacial properties of the adsorbed films of short chain monobasic and dibasic acids and their ions have received comparatively less attention so far. Elaborate and organised efforts have been made in our laboratory for the last fifteen years to obtain systematic interfacial and surface tension data for lower members of the monocarboxylic and dicarboxylic acids and their sodium salts under identical experimental conditions and to analyse these data in terms of the equation of state and the change of free energies for neutral and ionised films.

Surface and interfacial tensions of the oil-water and air-water systems in the presence of solute were measured at 35° by a modified drop-volume method using an Agla micrometer syringe¹⁶. The aqueous phases were pure water or solution of inorganic salt whereas non-aqueous phases used were n-heptane, petrol-ether, or benzene. The surface pressure of a soluble film at a given aqueous concentration C of the solute may be calculated from the relation,

$$\pi = \gamma_0 - \gamma \quad \dots (7)$$

where γ and γ_0 are the boundary tensions of the aqueous solvents in the presence and absence of the organic solute respectively. The organic monobasic acids¹⁶ used were n-butyric acid, n-valeric acid, n-caproic acid and n-caprylic acid having 4, 5, 6 and 8 carbon atoms respectively. The organic dibasic acids¹⁷ used were pimelic acid, suberic acid, azelaic acid and sebacic acid having 7, 8, 9 and 10 carbon atoms respectively. The pHs of the acid solutions were kept below 3.0 so that all acids remained in the unionised form both in the bulk and interfacial phases.

For each acid, π has been plotted against C and the value of the slope $\frac{d\pi}{dC}$ at a given value of C has been estimated graphically. The area per adsorbed organic molecule has been calculated from the Gibbs adsorption equation, written in an appropriate form of molar concentration scale

$$\frac{1}{A} = \frac{C}{kT} \frac{d\pi}{dC} \quad \dots (8)$$

π -A curves for all the four monobasic acids at the oil-water interfaces are found to be identical¹⁸. The pressure-area curves of the odd and even-chain dibasic acids, on the other hand, are different from each other. All the experimental π -A curves are observed to deviate considerably from the curve to be expected from the ideal equation

$$\pi A = kT \quad \dots (9)$$

Here k is the Boltzmann constant and T , the absolute temperature. The general equation of state of a gaseous neutral film may be written in the form¹⁸,

$$(\pi + \pi_s)(A - A_0) = kT \quad \dots (10)$$

where A_0 is the limiting co-area of the adsorbed molecule. According to Langmuir¹⁸, the cohesive pressure π_s for the film at the oil-water interface is zero since the hydrocarbon parts of the adsorbed molecules are unable to attract one another because these are surrounded by the hydrocarbon solvent. The Langmuir equation of state for the oil-water interface may then be written in the linear form¹⁹,

$$A = \frac{kT}{\pi} + A_0 \quad \dots (11)$$

Plots of A against $\frac{1}{\pi}$ for all the four acid systems belonging to both monobasic and dibasic groups are observed to be linear^{16,17}. The intercepts of these plots give the value of A_0 , the limiting co-area of an adsorbed molecule. The average value of A_0 for all the four monobasic acids is 24 square angstrom whereas values of A_0 for odd and even chain dibasic acids are observed to be 51 and 34 \AA^2 per molecule. The values of A_0 are consistent with the probable conformations of the adsorbed acids at the oil-water interface. However, the results on pressure-area values conclusively indicate that the hydrocarbon chains of the monobasic and dibasic acids existing at the oilside of the interface lose their ability to attract each other irrespective of their configuration. The molecules in such monolayers are perfectly mobile.

Adsorption isotherms and adsorption energies of neutral films :

If the molecules in the adsorbed film are perfectly nonlocalized or mobile, the area A per adsorbed molecule will be related to the bulk concentration C of the solute according to the modified Langmuir equation¹⁹,

$$\frac{A_0}{A - A_0} \exp\left(\frac{A_0}{A - A_0}\right) = \frac{C}{55.2} \exp\left(\frac{-\Delta G_0}{RT}\right) \quad \dots (12)$$

Here $-\Delta G_0$ is the adsorption energy or the decrease in the free energy due to the adsorption of one mole of solute from the solution. When left hand side of this equation calculated from the experimental data is plotted against C for the monobasic and dibasic acids, straight line is obtained in each case^{16,17}. The validity of equation (12) further suggests that the monobasic and dibasic acid molecules within the monolayer at an oil-water interface is perfectly non-localized due to lack of interchain

cohesion. The free energies of adsorption calculated from the slopes of these linear plots are presented in tables 1 and 2. From the scrutiny of the results given in table 1, the average adsorption energy $-\Delta G_{\text{OH}_2}^\circ$ per CH_2 group of the monobasic acid at the benzene-water interface has been found to be 760 calories per mole. We have also shown that $-\Delta G_{\text{OH}_2}^\circ$ will be only 545 calories per mole if the salt of the monobasic acids are used in place of the unionised acid¹⁶.

TABLE-1. ADSORPTION ENERGIES ($-\Delta G^\circ$) OF THE SHORT CHAIN ACIDS AND THEIR SALTS AT OIL-WATER INTERFACES (35°C)

Organic acid and the oil-water system	Adsorption energy of the neutral acid $-\Delta G^\circ$ (cal/mole)	Adsorption energy of the sodium salt of the acid $-\Delta G^\circ$ (cal/mole)
n-Butyric (B/W)	3,907	1,232
n-Valeric (B/W)	4,606	1,858
n-Caproic (B/W)	5,428	2,328
n-Caprylic (B/W)	6,927	3,415
n-Caprylic (P.E/W)	7,565	3,614

TABLE-2. ADSORPTION ENERGIES ($-\Delta G^\circ$) OF DIBASIC ACIDS AT OIL-WATER INTERFACES.

Organic compound and oil-water system	$-\Delta G^\circ$ calories mole	$-\Delta G^\circ \text{CH}_2$ cal/mole
Pimelic (H/W)	5651	714
Azelaic (H/W)	7080	
Suberic (H/W)	5939	714
Sebacic (H/W)	7367	
Sebacic (B/W)	6694	

From table 2, it is noted that the difference in the energies of adsorption between C_9 and C_7 dibasic acids as well as that between C_{10} and C_8 dibasic acids is 1428 calories per mole. The free energy of adsorption per CH_2 group calculated in this manner is 714 calories per mole when odd and even chain acids are grouped separately. The lower magnitude of $\Delta G_{\text{OH}_2}^\circ$ for the dibasic acids is possibly due to the relative rigidity in its structure because of their peculiar conformations at the interface.

Cohesive pressure at the air-water interface :

The cohesive attractive pressure π_s existing within a monolayer at the air-water interface is an interesting film property the magnitude of which is usually estimated from the relation²⁰

$$\pi_s = \pi_{\text{O/W}} - \pi_{\text{A/W}} \quad \dots (13)$$

where $\pi_{\text{A/W}}$ and $\pi_{\text{O/W}}$ are the surface pressures exerted by the adsorbed monolayer at the air-water and oil-water interfaces respectively at a given area per adsorbed molecule or ion. From the comparison of the pressure-area curves of the monobasic and dibasic acids at the oil-water and air-water interfaces, π_s for various values of A have been evaluated from the experimental data. From a

theoretical consideration, π_s is shown to be related to A by the equation²¹ :

$$\pi_s = \frac{a_s}{A^2} \quad \dots (14)$$

where a_s is the two-dimensional analog of the van der Waals attraction constant for the hydrocarbon parts of the gaseous surface film. π_s for both monobasic²² and dibasic acids¹⁷ is found to vary linearly with $1/A^2$ in agreement with equation (14), provided the area is not too small. The slopes of these straight lines representing a_s are given in table 3. For both monobasic and dibasic acids, a_s is observed to increase with increase of chain length.

or vertically oriented. τ' calculated from the experimental data²² are found from table 3 to be very close to τ_m , the length of the vertically oriented molecule.

The Gibbs equation for adsorption of the organic ions :

The form of the Gibbs adsorption equation(8) is strictly valid provided the solute component in the binary solution is a nonelectrolyte when an organic electrolyte (RCOONa, NaOOC-R-COONa) in the presence of neutral salt NaCl is adsorbed at the air-water or oil-water interfaces, the hydrocarbon part of the long-chain ions possibly remains in the oil-side of the surface, whereas the charged COO⁻ may

TABLE—3. VAN DER WAALS CONSTANT OF THE MONOLAYERS AT A/W INTERFACE

Acid Monolayer	$a_s \times 10^{18}$ ergs. cm ² molecule ²	$a \times 10^{34}$ ergs. cm ³ molecule ²	τ in Å°	τ in Å°	τ_m in Å°
Butyric	0.80	0.26	32.5	7.8	7.9
Valeric	1.29	0.38	29.4	9.9	9.1
Caproic	1.69	0.53	31.4	12.5	10.4
Caprylic	2.92	0.86	29.4	15.7	12.9

The value of the attraction $a_s^{OH_2}$ per CH₂ group is calculated by dividing a_s by the number of CH₂ groups present in the adsorbed solute. From the graphical comparison, $a_s^{OH_2}$ for a dibasic acid is observed to be considerably less than that of the monobasic acid¹⁷. The hydrocarbon chain in the film of monobasic acid orients perpendicularly at the interface so that it has maximum freedom for the two dimensional attraction. On the other hand, the dibasic acid within the film may form only a vertical loop as a result of which the attractive interaction between the chain in the film becomes considerably restricted.

For the films of monobasic acids, originally we have suggested that the thickness τ of the surface film may be estimated from the relation²¹

$$\tau = \frac{a}{a_s} \quad \dots (15)$$

Here 'a' stands for the three dimensional van der Waals constant of the gaseous hydrocarbon containing the same number of CH₂ groups as that of the surface active acid. From the table, calculated from equation (14) are found to be considerably larger in magnitude than vertical length of the organic monobasic acid. Recently from thermodynamic consideration, Gershfeld²³ has shown that the exact film thickness τ' should be related to a_s and a by the equation

$$\tau' = \frac{a}{a_s + kTA} \quad \dots (16)$$

provided the adsorbed molecules are fully stretched

be oriented towards the aqueous side of the phase boundary. Below the negatively charged interfacial plane on the aqueous side, small inorganic ions (Na⁺, Cl⁻ etc.) are believed to be distributed unequally with the formation of the electrical double layer at the interface. If the adsorbed organic ions and equivalent number of counterions (Na⁺) respectively at the interface are imagined to remain on two parallel planes at a molecular distance apart, a Helmholtz type of the double layer is formed. In a more realistic picture proposed by Gouy, the positively and negatively charged inorganic ions in the double layer are imagined to be distributed in an extended space within the surface region in accordance with the Boltzmann distribution principle. Mukherjee²⁴ and Stern²⁵ have subsequently proposed that part of the counterions in the double layer is specifically bound to the adsorbed organic counterions, whereas the rest of the inorganic ions are distributed in the diffuse layer following the Boltzmann distribution principle. The picture of the electrical double layer has been refined and modified frequently in the last fifty years²⁶.

When an organic ion of valency Z resulting from the ionisation of the organic electrolyte RNaz is adsorbed from the bulk to the liquid interface in the presence of constant concentration of the neutral salt (NaCl), Gibbs equation has been shown to assume a general form²⁷,

$$\frac{1}{A} = \left[\frac{C_R}{mkT} \frac{d\tau}{dC_R} \right] \quad \dots (17)$$

Here m is termed the kT- coefficient of the Gibbs equation. Several attempts²⁷⁻³⁴ have been made by us to obtain theoretically a general expression.

for m , assuming electroneutrality in the surface and the bulk phases. Finally it has been settled^{35,36} that

$$m = \xi \left[1 + \frac{Z^2 \phi}{Z + \frac{C_B}{C_R} f(\psi_\delta)} \right] \quad \dots (18)$$

in which Z is the charge of the organic ion and $f(\psi_\delta)$ is a function whose value depends on the nature and magnitude of the potential (ψ_δ) of the electrical double layer; C_B stands for the concentration of the neutral salt. The values of ξ and ϕ on the basis of the limiting law are given by the equation³⁰,

$$\xi = \left[1 - \frac{2.303 \bar{A} Z^3 (Z+1) C_R}{2 Z Z (Z+1) C_R + 4 C_S} \right] \quad \dots (19)$$

and

$$\phi = \frac{2\sqrt{2Z(Z+1)C_R + 4C_S} - 2.303\bar{A}(Z+1)(ZC_R + C_S)}{2\sqrt{2Z(Z+1)C_R + 4C_S} - 2.303\bar{A}Z^2(Z+1)C_R} \quad \dots (20)$$

where A stands for the Debye-Hückel constant. Complicated expressions for $f(\psi_\delta)$ assuming Gouy and Stern models for electrical double layer have been derived by us. Very recently³⁷, expressions for ξ and ϕ have been obtained on the basis of the extended Debye-Hückel theories and the application of equation (17) for the bolaform electrolytes has been discussed.

For Helmholtz double layer, $f(\psi_\delta)$ is unity and this may be used with sacrifice of less than ten per cent accuracy for the uncertain feature of the electrical double layer model³⁸. The suitable forms of the Gibbs equations have further considered by us in great detail for various complicated cases of multicomponent solutions^{35,36}.

π -A curves of the ionised monolayer :

Salts of octanoic, sebacic, azelaic and suberic acids were prepared by titrating the pure dibasic acids with sodium hydroxide (in few cases with LiOH and KOH)^{38,39}. The pHs of the solutions were kept close to 11.0 by adding slight excess of alkali. The aqueous solutions of the salts of the acids in the presence and absence of 1M sodium chloride were kept in contact with the oil at 35° for 8 hours. The equilibrated aqueous phase was then separated from the oil phase and the interfacial tensions of the oil-water systems were measured by using the Agla micrometer syringe as before. On plotting the interfacial pressure π against concentrations C_R of these acids, it has been observed^{38,39} that π depends significantly on chain length of the organic solute, the nature of the oil phase and the nature and concentration of the inorganic salt.

From the π - C_R plot, the area A per adsorbed organic ion has been calculated using Gibbs equation (17) and equation (18) for the kT -coefficient. For the sebacate monolayer without neutral salt³⁹, m varies from 2.67 to 1.47 due to change of C_R from 0.0025M to 0.06M. In the presence of neutral salt, m in all cases becomes unity. From graphical comparison, π - A curves of ionised monolayers of dibasic acids are observed to differ from corresponding π - A curves of the neutral monolayer. The π - A curve of the sebacate monolayer is slightly affected by the nature of the oil phase but it has strong dependence on the nature of the cations attached to the organic and inorganic salts³⁹.

At a given value of A , the experimental value of electrical pressure π_o may be calculated directly from the difference $\pi - \pi_o$. Here π and π_o represents the surface pressures of the ionised salts and the unionised acids respectively. From Gouy-Davies equation, the theoretical value of electrical pressure (π'_o) may also be calculated for sebacate using equation (21).

$$\pi'_o = \int_0^{\psi_\delta} \sigma d\psi = 6.2\sqrt{C_R + C_S} \left[\left\{ \frac{137^2}{\left(\frac{A}{2}\right)^2 (C_R + C_S)} + 1 \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} - 1 \right] \quad \dots (21)$$

Here σ and ψ stand for the charge and potential of the electrical double layer. π_o - A and π'_o - A curves are observed to differ widely. This indicates that the Gouy model of the electrical double layer is inadequate to interpret experimental data.

In the opinion of Bell, Levine and Pethica⁴⁰, the inequality between the experimental π_o and theoretical π'_o is due to the neglect of the fluctuation pressure π_f which in fact may arise due to the discrete nature of the interfacial charge. According to the BLP theory⁴⁰, the correct value of the electrical pressure is π''_o , which may be calculated from the equation,

$$\pi''_o = \pi'_o + \pi_f \quad \dots (22)$$

Following the complicated expression for π_f , π''_o for various values of A have been estimated by us³⁹. π''_o - A plot is also observed to widely differ from π_o - A curve. At high pressure region, π_o is observed to be negative whereas π'_o and π''_o are both positive. This apparently indicates the imperfection of the models of the electrical double layer so far used by us.

In our opinion³⁹, all these discrepancies occur due to the neglect of the effect of binding of counterions by the charged monolayers in the theoretical

calculation of the charged monolayer. Such a binding may eventually reduce ψ_δ as a result of which the electrical pressure may be considerably reduced. Relation (22) should then be written in the modified form,

$$\pi_e = \pi'_e + \pi_f + \Delta\pi_b \quad \dots (23)$$

$$\text{and } \pi_e^0 = \pi_e - \pi_f = \pi'_e + \Delta\pi_b \quad \dots (24)$$

Here $\Delta\pi_b$ stands for the reduction in the electrical pressure due to the binding of counter-ions. π_e^0 is the electrical pressure generated at the charged interface such that the double layer model is of the perfect Stern-Gouy type and the discrete ion effect at the interface is absent. For a fixed electrical pressure, let A'_e and A_e^0 be the corresponding values of the area per molecule in the π'_e -A and π_e^0 -A plots respectively. The fraction (F') of COO⁻ ions within the adsorbed film binding counterions may then be calculated from the relation

$$F' = 1 - \frac{A_e^0}{A'_e} \quad \dots (25)$$

The values of F' for various values of A in the case of sebacate monolayers have been calculated by us³⁹.

The pressure-area curve of charged and neutral monolayers of octanoate and octanoic acid monolayers^{36,37} have also been critically compared in the light of the BLP theory. The deviation from the BLP theory is also observed to be quite significant.

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